

1 **Small molecules that enhance immunity or have lifespan extension potential.**

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7 Lifespan extension is an ultimate goal whose motivation can be disputed to be medical or cosmetic. In a
8 population affected by cancer, immune augmentation or enhancement can have equivalent effects to a
9 lifespan extension product. We integrated multiple systems-level approaches to identify and describe
10 genes functioning in, for discovery of therapeutic targets whose inhibition with a small molecule could have
11 enhance immunity or have lifespan extension potential. Here we studied by genetic depletion and
12 transcriptome sequencing a family of nuclear receptors known as *Tox*. In CAR-T cells with genetic
13 depletion of *Tox*, cells activated genes functioning in iron recycling and homeostasis associated with
14 aging, including ferrochelatase *FECH* and ferritin heavy chain *FTH*. *Tox* depleted cells displayed signs of
15 altered cell death signaling including loss of *PSAT1* expression and repression of *PDCD5*. Cells with
16 forced silencing of *Tox* lost expression of *RAD23A*, activated *FEM1C*, and silenced the oxidoreductase-like
17 domain containing 1, *OXML1*. propose inhibition of modulation of the one or more of the *Tox* family
18 nuclear receptors could exert lifespan extension.

19 Citations

20 1. Guarente, L. and Kenyon, C., 2000. Genetic pathways that regulate ageing in model organisms.
21 *Nature*, 408(6809), pp.255-262.

22 2. Ladiges, W., Van Remmen, H., Strong, R., Ikeno, Y., Treuting, P., Rabinovitch, P. and Richardson,
23 A., 2009. Lifespan extension in genetically modified mice. *Aging cell*, 8(4), pp.346-352.

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